

A short taxonomic note on the buthid taxa described by Rafat Amir et al. (Scorpiones: Buthidae)

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Remarks

The discovery of two new species of genus *Razianus* Farzanpay, 1987 from Pakistan (Tahir et al., 2014), alongside the general morphology, may suggest its closer relationship with *Hemibuthus* (from India and Pakistan). They can be, however, as stated by a few authors, distinguished by the carapacial carinae (absent in *Hemibuthus*, but distinct in *Razianus*) and trichobothrial pattern (α -configuration on pedipalp femur and A- α on chela in *Razianus* vs. β -configuration on pedipalp femur and A- β on chela in *Hemibuthus*) (Birula, 1903: 77; Lourenço, 1996: 93; Fet, 1997: 66). For *Hemibuthus*, the first character is obvious as depicted in Lourenço (1996: fig. 1) which, however, did not match with the illustration by Tikader & Bastawade (1983: 286–287) that showed a pair of central median and posterior median carinae. A second species was described by Amir et al. (2004b) as *H. umarii* Amir, Kamaluddin & Khan, 2004 from Rohri and Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan, suffered from a poor description and illustrations. Several characters were quite perplexing, such as the presence of a mere 3 rows of denticles on the pedipalp fingers (*op. cit.*: 490) and the statement of a short aculeus (*op. cit.*: 494), which, judging from the photo, appeared to be broken. In conjunction with the known distribution in Pakistan, total length, PTC, and the mere two photographs of *H. umarii* in its original description, it is most likely a junior subjective synonym of *Odontobuthus odonturus* (Pocock, 1897) (Barahoei et al., 2021: 37). Nonetheless, the original statement that *H. umarii* has an entirely smooth carapace surface with smooth carinae refrains this assumption, and a re-examination of the type is required to unravel its status.

An inadvertent glimpse of another Pakistani species in the genus *Compsobuthus* Vachon, 1949 from Digri (Sindh) by the same group of authors, *C. humaae* Amir, Kamaluddin & Khan, 2005, at least confirmed my assumption for its generic subordination under *Odontobuthus* Vachon, 1950 as a more clear photograph was included in the original description (Amir et al., 2005b: fig. 1). Uncertainty nonetheless remains as to its validity within *Odontobuthus*. Coincidentally, Deshpande et al. (2023: 94) have just reached the same conclusion for the two *Isometrus* species described by those authors, namely *I. (Reddyanus) atherii* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2008 and *I. (Isometrus) liaqatii* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2008. It thus appears that this is not an incident of mere happenstance, which motivated me to inspect other species described by those authors.

Likewise, after reviewing the photographs they included for their new species (Amir et al., 2004a: fig. 1; Amir & Kamaluddin, 2009: figs. 1–2, 12–13), it became evident that *Buthotus asimii* Amir et al., 2004 (from Moro, Sindh), *Vachonus asiyaee* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2009 and *V. iqbali* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2009 (both from Chachro, Sindh) do not belong to the genera where they were originally assigned to. The strongly serrated (tooth-like) ventrosubmedian (on metasoma II–III) and ventrolateral carinae (on metasoma V), bulbous vesicle, large median ocelli and infuscate preocular regions promote *B. asimii* and *V. iqbali* to be classified under *Odontobuthus*, while the weak metasomal carinae, strong mesosomal carinae, and small and anterior median ocelli suggest the subordination of *V. asiyaee* within *Compsobuthus*.

As for the two species described under the genus *Stenochirus* Oppel, 1862 (junior subjective synonym of *Buthoscorpio* Werner, 1936) by Amir et al. (2005a) from Malir, Sindh, *S. jinnahii* and *S. rahmatii*, only the former species was provided with two relatively observable photographs (Amir et al., 2005a: figs. 1–2). Both species were described as possessing 29 pectinal teeth in the dichotomous keys (*op. cit.*: 532), but this count shifted to 20 in the description of *S. jinnahii* (*op. cit.*: 532) while returned to 29 in other sections (*op. cit.*: 535), which may imply a typographic error given the adjacency between 9 and 0 on the keyboard. Neither PTC matches the generic diagnosis for *Buthoscorpio* (PTC < 18) as per Javed et al. (2010: 5), who also posed their doubts on the taxonomic status of the two species. According to the only available photographs, it appears that Amir et al. (2005a) once again described their “new” species with *Odontobuthus* specimens. The light-colored, semioval preocular region was confined at the first 1/3 of the short, quadrate carapace (*op. cit.*: fig. 1), suggesting an anterior position of the median ocelli, as well as the infuscate margin of the carapace, conforming with the characters of *Odontobuthus*. Although the photos for the second species were shrouded in pitch black (*op. cit.*: figs. 14–15) and the descriptions by those authors cannot be trusted (given that they considered their *Odontobuthus* specimen “very closely related to” *Compsobuthus atrostriatus* (Pocock, 1897); Amir & Kamaluddin, 2009: 22), it is

speculated that this specimen again represented an *Odontobuthus* sp.

Conclusively, the following taxa most likely belong to genus *Odontobuthus*: *Buthotus asimii* Amir et al., 2004; *Compsobuthus humaae* Amir et al., 2005; *Hemibuthus umarii* Amir et al., 2004; *Stenochirus jinnahii* Amir et al., 2005; *Stenochirus rahmatii* Amir et al., 2005; *Vachonus iqbali* Amir et al., 2009. On the other hand, *Vachonus asiyaee* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2009 may represent a *Compsobuthus* species. All those taxa currently remain as *nomina dubia*. However, I suspect that all the species potentially belonged to *Odontobuthus* are synonymous, including the two species excluded from *Isometrus* by [Deshpande et al. \(2023\)](#): *Odontobuthus* (ex. *Isometrus* (*Reddyanus*)) *atherii* and *O.* (ex. *Isometrus* (*Isometrus*)) *liaqatii*.

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